

2023 ANNUAL REPORT

**FROM AMBITION TO ACTION:
FOSTERING RESEARCH
EXCELLENCE IN EUROPE**

**SCIENCE
EUROPE**
Shaping the future of research

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PREFACE

**Through exchange and mutual learning
Science Europe fosters co-operation, innovation,
and excellence in research across Europe,
and globally. Our collaborative initiatives,
including CoARA, reflect a steadfast commitment
to reshaping assessment practices to enhance
research integrity and quality worldwide.**

MARC SCHILTZ / PRESIDENT OF SCIENCE EUROPE, 2017-2023

FOREWORD

It is my privilege to introduce this Annual Report, which highlights the association's key activities in 2023. As I reflect not only on last year, but on the entire six years I was President of Science Europe, I would like to pay tribute to my colleagues in the Governing Board for their strategic input and continuing support, as well as to the members of our Working Groups, on whose expertise and engagement we rely. Their diverse perspectives and specialised knowledge enrich our discussions and enhance the relevance and quality of our work.

At the forefront of our achievements in 2023 to develop a research culture where all researchers can thrive, was the first Global Summit on Diamond Open Access. This brought together a worldwide community that is committed to opening the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation, and communication to build a transparent, equitable, and inclusive scholarly communication ecosystem. Further efforts to advance research quality were made by our continuing prioritisation of the reform of research assessment, both as a leading partner of the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#), and through the publication of our own [Recommendations](#) on how research organisations can continuously improve the way they assess research and researchers – the culmination of a two-year project. Additionally, our survey on diversity in research organisations provided the foundation for the development of [new guidance](#) (released in 2024) to ensure that all roles within the research community are accessible and accommodating to all.

We worked with our partners at European and global level, contributing to important conversations on the European Research Area and ensuring there are strong connections between these discussions and the Horizon Europe Framework Programmes. We continued to highlight the lack of adequate funding and advocated a better balance between applied and fundamental research, as well as the need to prioritise reducing disparities in research and innovation capacity across the EU.

Reciprocity and equity in international collaboration was a key theme of the [15th High-Level Workshop on the ERA](#), and efforts are ongoing to advance this dialogue with European institutions and national governments to build long-term research collaborations, guided by a shared commitment to principles of academic freedom, scientific integrity, equity, reciprocity, and non-discrimination.

The contributions that science can make to tackle the many and complex societal challenges we face was underlined in the publication of our [Report on science-policy interfaces](#). We worked with our members to identify how best to amplify the voice of science and bridge the gap between researchers and society, laying the foundations for a [High-level Conference on Science Communication](#) in 2024. Responding to the rapid developments in Artificial Intelligence, we also began important conversations with our members to support them to better understand, harness, and navigate the challenges and potential of this transformational tool in research systems and processes. Running through all our activities has been our unwavering support for the National Research Foundation of Ukraine and their efforts to develop Ukrainian research systems in the face of ongoing aggression.

MARC SCHILTZ /
PRESIDENT OF SCIENCE EUROPE, 2017-2023

“As we look back on 2023, I want to acknowledge the collective efforts of our members, partners, and stakeholders in advancing our mission, as well as the dedication of the Science Europe staff. We remain steadfast in our commitment to enhancing the research landscape, addressing global challenges, and promoting a culture of excellence, diversity, and sustainability in research.”

2023 AT A GLANCE

Q1

JANUARY

30 January: First CoARA Steering Board Meeting

FEBRUARY

- 11 February:** Launch of [Empowering Women in Science](#) campaign between International Day of Women and Girls in Science and International Women's Day
- 22 February:** Publication of [Response to Public Consultation on Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe](#)
- 23-24 February:** Attended workshop on 'An EU copyright & data legislative framework fit for research: barriers, challenges and potential measures'

MARCH

- 21 March:** 2nd Ukraine Conference and Joint Meeting with National Research Foundation of Ukraine on 'Professional development on research management and European integration.'
- 21 March:** Position Statement on Support for the Establishment of the International Centre for Mathematics in Ukraine

- 24 March:** Publication of [How to Become an Effective Science-Policy Advisor? 16 Lessons Learned](#)
- 29 March:** Publication of [Science-Policy in Action: Insights for the Green and Digital Transition](#)

Q2

APRIL

- 4 April:** Launch of survey on Equality, Diversity and Inclusion within Research Systems
- 17 April:** Diamond Open Access Community Webinar
- 20 April:** Publication of [Interdisciplinarity for the Net-Zero Transition: the Perspectives of Universities and Research Organisations](#)
- 27 April:** Publication of [Recognising What We Value: Recommendations on Recognition Systems](#)

MAY

- 4 May:** Publication of [Science Europe Conference Report on Open Science](#)
- 4 May:** Science Europe signs [San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment \(DORA\)](#)
- 17 May:** The Austrian Academy of Sciences (OeAW) joins Science Europe
- 23 May:** Publication of [Joint Statement on Council Conclusions on Not-for-Profit Scholarly Communication Ecosystem](#)
- 26 May:** 1st Meeting of the Science Europe CoARA Forum
- 31 May-1 June:** Participated in the 2023 Global Research Council Annual Meeting (The Hague, Netherlands)

JUNE

- 1 June:** Organised GRC Side Event 'Making Research Assessment Reform a Global Endeavour' (The Hague, Netherlands)
- 5, 21, 28 June:** Joint Workshop Series on 'Preserving and Developing Ukraine's Human Capital in Research, Education, and Innovation,' with the National Academies of Sciences Engineering and Medicine in the USA (NASEM)
- 23 June:** Participated in first CoARA General Assembly
- 30 June:** Publication of [2022 Annual Report: Research at the Heart of Europe's Ambition](#)

Q3

JULY

- 20 July:** Publication of a statement [calling for caution in discussing phasing out of the use of animals in research](#)

SEPTEMBER

- 6 September:** Webinar on Open Research Methods
- 10-27 September:** Participated in UN Science Summit (New York, USA)
- 25-27 September:** Participated in Open Science Fair
- 27 September:** Participated in 2nd ESFRI Stakeholder Forum
- 28 September:** Internal Workshop 'Artificial Intelligence in Science: the role of Research Funding and Performing Organisations'

Q4

OCTOBER

- 9 October:** Participated in INFN International School of Science Communication and Journalism Summer School on the Big Data society (Erice, Italy)
- 9-10 October:** Internal Workshop on 'The Roles and Opportunities of Science Europe Member Organisations for the Green and Digital Transition' (Brussels, Belgium)
- 19-21 October:** Participated in Connect. Collaborate.Create. Conference 'Bridging Communities for Participatory Research and Citizen Science' (Paris, France)
- 23-27 October:** [Diamond Open Access Global Summit](#) (Toluca, México)
- 25-26 October:** [2nd Diamond Open Access Conference](#) (Toluca, México)

NOVEMBER

- 3 November:** Publication of '[Conclusions and Way Forward from the Global Summit on Diamond Open Access](#)'
- 8-10 November:** Participated in the G7 Working Group on Research Assessment
- 20-22 November:** [2023 European Regional Meeting of the Global Research Council](#) (Bucharest, Romania)
- 29-30 November:** [15th High level workshop on the ERA](#) (Madrid, Spain)

DECEMBER

- 7 December:** Publication of '[Statement on International Research Collaboration](#)'
- 7-8 December:** Launch of the CoARA Boost Project
- 15 December:** Participated in CoARA General Assembly and elected to Steering Board

TOP ACHIEVEMENTS

Publication of the Science Europe **Response to the Public Consultation on Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe** containing many recommendations on future European R&I programmes.

Continuing **support** for the **National Research Foundation of Ukraine**.

Publication of the survey-based report **'Science-Policy in Action: Insights for the Green and Digital Transition'** launched at a high level event with Marc Lemaître, newly appointed Director General for Research and Innovation, European Commission.

Continuing support for the reform of research assessment as a leading partner in **CoARA** and our advocacy towards the European institutions and in the **Global Research Council**.

Publication of the report **'Recognising What We Value'** highlighting how Member Organisations foster a positive and nurturing research culture.

The organisation of the first **Global Summit on Diamond Open Access** with nine other partners, in support of more sustainable, equitable Open Access models.

Joint organisation by CSIC and Science Europe of the **2023 High Level Workshop** on 'Challenges to reciprocity and equitable scientific collaboration between Europe, Africa, Latin America, and the Caribbean' under the auspices of the Spanish Presidency of the Council of the EU.

Planning of the **High Level Conference on Science Communication** with FNRS and FWO, under the auspices of the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the EU.

Development of a framework to assess the strategic value of international research collaboration.

MEET THE MEMBERS

1 FWF Österreichischer Wissenschaftsfonds	2 ÖAW ÖSTERREICHISCHE AKADEMIE DER WISSENSCHAFTEN	3 fnrs LA LIBERTÉ DE CHERCHER	4 fwo Research Foundation Flanders Opening new horizons
5 HRZZ Croatian Science Foundation	6 GAČR CZECH SCIENCE FOUNDATION	7 INDEPENDENT RESEARCH FUND DENMARK	8 Danmarks Grundforskningsfond Danish National Research Foundation
9 Estonian Research Council	10 Research Council of Finland	11 anr [®] agence nationale de la recherche	12 DFG Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft German Research Foundation
13 HUN-REN Hungarian Research Network	14 MTA HUNGARIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES	15 rannís	16 HRB Health Research Board
17 IRISH RESEARCH COUNCIL An Chomhairle um Theaghlóid in Éire	18 sfi Science Foundation Ireland For what's next	19 INFN Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare	20 Latvian Council of Science
21 Lietuvos mokslo taryba	22 ENR	23 NWO	24 Research Council of Norway
25 FNP Foundation for Polish Science	26 NATIONAL SCIENCE CENTRE	27 fct Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia	28 uefiscidi
29 Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia	30 SLOVAK RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AGENCY	31 amis Science Research and Innovation Agency	32 eI
33 CSIC Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	34 i3c Instituto de Salud Carlos III	35 FORTE: Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare	36 FORMAS
37 Vetenskapsrådet	38 Swiss National Science Foundation	39 NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION OF UKRAINE	40 UKRI UK Research and Innovation

2023 IN NUMBERS

MEMBERSHIP

40

MEMBERS

29

EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

CONTRIBUTING (APPROX.)

€25.1
BILLION

TO RESEARCH PER YEAR

PUBLICATIONS

11

POLICY POSITIONS,
GUIDELINES & REPORTS

31

HIGH-LEVEL PRESS MENTIONS

EVENTS

5

ONSITE EVENTS ORGANISED
BY SCIENCE EUROPE

116

EXTERNAL EVENTS
WITH CONTRIBUTIONS BY
SCIENCE EUROPE

25

MEETINGS OF SCIENCE EUROPE
GOVERNANCE AND WORKING
GROUPS

SOCIAL MEDIA

485k

IMPRESSIONS

14,2k

FOLLOWERS

144k

IMPRESSIONS

7,6k

FOLLOWERS

WEBSITE

35k

WEBSITE VISITORS

112k

WEBSITE PAGE VIEWS

NEWSLETTERS

11

MEMBER NEWSLETTERS

2

PUBLIC NEWSLETTERS

Science Europe updates July 2023
Science Europe updates January 2024

9

VIDEO PRODUCTIONS

- [New Year's Message to Science Europe Member Organisations](#)
- [High level workshop on ERA 2023 wrap-up](#)
- [Women in Science Interview with Maria Cruz](#)
- [Women in Science Interview with Carolina Cañibano](#)
- [Women in Science Interview with Anneli Allik](#)
- [Women in Science Interview with Lidia Borrell-Damián](#)
- [Women in Science Interview with Hannele Lahtinen](#)
- [Women in Science Interview with Krisztina Szepesvári](#)
- [#TalkingScience with high integrity and ethics standards](#)

SUPPORT FOR UKRAINE

As the conflict in Ukraine continues, Science Europe continues to offer unwavering support to the Ukrainian research ecosystem and its Member Organisation in the country, the National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU).

Science Europe and NRFU organised an event on supporting and managing the funding of scientific research grants during ongoing humanitarian emergencies and conflicts. This took place as a side-event to the second conference on the Ukraine crisis organised by the International Science Council (ISC) and the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities (ALLEA). It built on previous events drawing attention to the impact of the ongoing war on academia and scientific research. During the conference, Science Europe published a statement of support for the establishment of an International Mathematics Institute of Ukraine.

In June, Science Europe participated in a workshop on 'Preserving and Developing Ukraine's Human Capital in Research, Education, and Innovation,' organised by the US National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine (NASEM), where Science Europe Member Organisations NWO and NCN also shared their best practices. Additionally, Science Europe provides ongoing support through its participation in the NRFU Board of International Counsellors.

Visit the Science Europe website to find out how our members are supporting the people of Ukraine, including the research community.

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/ukraine/

GOVERNING BOARD MEMBERS 2021-2023

The Science Europe Governing Board is the senior body of elected members, which is entrusted by the General Assembly to define, guide, and monitor the strategic direction of the association. Elected in November 2021, it consists of at least nine Heads of Science Europe’s Member Organisations, including a President and two Vice-Presidents. Governing Board members are elected by the General Assembly for a term of two years.

Marc Schiltz
(President)
Secretary General
of the Luxembourg
National Research
Fund (FNR)
Luxembourg

Angelika Kalt
*(Vice-President
representing RFOs)*
Director of the
Swiss National
Science Foundation
(SNSF)
Switzerland

Marcel Levi
*(Vice-President
representing RPOs)*
President of the
Dutch Research
Council (NWO)
The Netherlands

**Francisco Javier
Moreno Fuentes**
Vice-President
for International
Affairs, Spanish
National Research
Council (CSIC)
Spain

Adrian Curaj
Director General
of the Executive
Agency for
Higher Education,
Research,
Development
and Innovation
Funding of Romania
(UEFISCDI)
Romania

Thierry Damerval
President/CEO
of the French
National Research
Agency (ANR)
France

Matthias Koenig
Vice-President
of the German
Research
Foundation (DFG)
Germany

Mari Sundli Tveit
Chief Executive
of the Research
Council of Norway
(RCN)
Norway

Melanie Welham
Executive Chair
of UK Research
and innovation
(UKRI)
United Kingdom
(until 30 June 2023)

Antonio Zoccoli
President of the
National Institute
for Nuclear Physics
(INFN)
Italy

GOVERNING BOARD MEMBERS 2023-2025

The following Governing Board members were elected in November 2023:

Mari Sundli Tveit
(President)
Chief Executive
of the Research
Council of Norway
(RCN)
Norway

Marcel Levi
*(Vice-President
representing RFOs)*
President of the
Dutch Research
Council (NWO)
The Netherlands

**Francisco Javier
Moreno Fuentes**
*(Vice-President
representing RPOs)*
Vice-President
for International
Affairs, Spanish
National Research
Council (CSIC)
Spain

Katarina Bjelke
Director General
of the Swedish
Research Council
(VR)
Sweden

Adrian Curaj
Director General
of the Executive
Agency for
Higher Education,
Research,
Development
and Innovation
Funding of Romania
(UEFISCDI)
Romania

Anna Di Ciaccio
Director of the
National Institute
for Nuclear Physics
(INFN)
Italy

**Milica Đurić-
Jovičić**
Acting Director
of the Science Fund
of the Republic of
Serbia (SFRS)
Serbia

**Christof
Gattringer**
President of the
Austrian Science
Fund (FWF)
Austria

Matthias Koenig
Vice-President
of the German
Research
Foundation (DFG)
Germany

**Christopher
Smith**
Executive Chair
of the Arts and
Humanities
Research Council,
UK Research and
Innovation
(UKRI)
United Kingdom

“It is an honour to have been elected President of Science Europe. Scientific research has never played a more critical role in tackling the challenges we face. I look forward to working with our dedicated members to advocate our common interests to build a stronger research environment for the creation of new scientific knowledge, and for the benefit of researchers and society.”

MARI SUNDLI TVEIT / PRESIDENT SCIENCE EUROPE (2023-2025)

VISION AND MISSION

Science Europe is the association representing major public organisations that fund or perform excellent, ground-breaking scientific research in Europe. It brings together the expertise of some of the largest and best-known research organisations in the world to jointly push the frontiers of how scientific research is produced and delivers benefits to society.

VISION

Science Europe's vision is for a European Research Area with optimal conditions to support robust education, research, and innovation systems. This is a European Research Area where science is a strong and trusted component of sustainable economic, environmental, and societal development.

MISSION

Science Europe's mission is to define long-term perspectives for European research and to champion best-practice approaches, ensuring high-quality science for the benefit of humanity and the planet.

REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

[Science Europe Strategy Plan 2021–2026](#)

[Multi-Annual Action Plan 2021–2026](#)

STRATEGY PLAN

The Strategy Plan has three strategic priorities that encapsulate Science Europe’s vision:

- Shape European research policy developments
- Contribute to the evolution of research culture
- Strengthen the role and contribution of science in tackling societal challenges

SCIENCE EUROPE STRATEGY PLAN PRIORITIES AND TOPICS

Our plans are continually reviewed and evaluated to reflect emerging priorities such as our new focus on the use of Artificial Intelligence in research processes and the impact of research activities on the environment.

REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

[Science Europe Strategy Plan 2021–2026](#)

[Multi-Annual Action Plan 2021–2026](#)

ACTIVITY AREAS

CONTRIBUTE TO THE EVOLUTION OF RESEARCH CULTURE

THE SCIENCE EUROPE STRATEGY PLAN / 2021-2026

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS

Driving global engagement for the open science movement through the first Global Summit on Diamond Open Access.

Developing a vision for the future of research based on shared values reflected in research policies and practices.

Consolidating activities for the reform of research assessment at both European and global levels.

RESEARCH CULTURE

Science Europe’s efforts in 2023 across research assessment reform, careers, diversity, integrity, and open science reflect our commitment to advancing research quality and fostering inclusive, positive, and innovative research environments, both in Europe and globally.

Through collaboration, advocacy, and proactive engagement, we strive to shape the future of research based on the 2022 framework of shared values, developed with the support of our members, and ensure they are reflected in research policies and practices. The publication of our report 'Recognising What We Value', provides a vision of what this future could look like.

As a leading partner of the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#) advocating at European and global level, Science Europe continued to prioritise the reform of research assessment. Through a survey of our members, we gathered information on their policies and best practices for Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion, as well as the challenges they face. This allowed us to develop updated guidance for research organisations (released in 2024) as part of our efforts to promote inclusion and equality in research.

Our contribution to the updated [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) reflected our commitment to policies which build trust in research and scholarship. Acknowledging the interconnections between research culture and open science, the first [Global Summit on Diamond Open Access](#) was a key milestone in driving global engagement for the movement.

RESEARCH CAREERS

The topic of research careers is a keystone for actions to improve research cultures. Science Europe continued to provide input to ongoing consultations in the European Research Area on a [European Framework for Research Careers](#) which was adopted by EU Ministers in December 2023. It promises many important advances to make research careers in Europe more attractive and sustainable, including improved recognition of open science as part of the careers of researchers. More broadly, we continued to focus on the concepts of 'the research profession' and 'careers in research', including recognition of the vital role that non-researcher roles play in our research systems, alongside recognition for researchers at all career stages. These issues will be explored in more detail in a workshop planned for 2024.

“Reform of research assessment is an intrinsic component of advancing a research culture which strives for quality and excellence and ensures that all participants in the research endeavour are appropriately recognised for their diverse contributions.”

MATTHIAS KOENIG / VICE-PRESIDENT OF THE GERMAN RESEARCH FOUNDATION (DFG)

The publication 'Recognising What We Value: Recommendations on Recognition Systems'.

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/research-culture

REFORM OF RESEARCH ASSESSMENT

Science Europe continued to prioritise the reform of research assessment, consolidating the achievements of 2022, and offering a reappraisal of institutional approaches and values, to create a research environment that nurtures innovation.

Momentum on reforming research assessment continues to grow. Science Europe was instrumental in establishing the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), launched on 1 December 2022. It now brings together 637 organisations (including 35 Science Europe members), committed to research assessment that is based primarily on qualitative judgment rather than quantitative indicators.

During 2023 we focused on building synergies between CoARA's future work and our own activities. As well as contributing to the establishment of CoARA national chapters and working groups on different aspects of research assessment, and agreeing a series of activities to implement the Coalition's core commitments (published in 2024), Science Europe is a partner in the EU-funded CoARA Boost project, responsible for expanding the reach and growing the membership of CoARA in Europe and beyond. To this end, we organised a meeting at the Global Research Council on how best to tackle national and regional challenges which might prevent CoARA from becoming a truly global initiative.

There are now many international, multi-stakeholder initiatives that aim to improve the ways research ideas, researchers, and research organisations are assessed. The publication of 'Recognising What We Value: Recommendations on Recognition Systems', the outcome of a two-year project, presents a vision on how some aspects of these new research assessment systems could look. It also highlights best-practice examples from Science Europe members

of implementing recommendations based on the values which should underpin research assessment, such as respect for research autonomy; care and collegiality; collaboration; equality, diversity and inclusion; integrity and ethics; and openness and transparency.

Science Europe also formalised its long and fruitful relationship with DORA – the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment, reinforcing our joint commitment to the reform of research assessment in support of research quality. In November, we took part as an observer at the G7 Working Group on Research Assessment, which was an opportunity to present our work in support of the advancement of new ways of assessing research in a global context.

“Moving to systems of research assessment based on qualitative evaluation over quantitative indicators will allow good ideas to flourish and talented people to thrive.”

ANGELIKA KALT / DIRECTOR OF THE SWISS NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION (SNSF)

coara.eu

A series of activities to support CoARA was published in 2024.

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/research-assessment

EQUALITY, DIVERSITY, AND INCLUSION

Gender equality and diversity are essential components of a system that produces scientific excellence. Science Europe works to promote a research environment where all scholars can realise their potential regardless of their gender, sexual orientation, religion, disabilities, ethnic origin, or social background. Promoting diversity in research is not only a moral imperative, but also a means of supporting research quality, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the increasingly complex challenges that our R&I systems face.

During 2023, we focused our efforts on two levels: launching a dedicated survey of our members to investigate the current situation regarding diversity in research organisations across Europe; and at global level through the [Global Research Council's EDI Working Group](#), which Science Europe co-chairs.

The survey, launched in April, collected information on our members' EDI policies, the challenges they face, and good practices currently being implemented, to update our 2017 guidance on improving gender equality in research organisations.

The practical recommendations contained in the [new guidance](#), published in early 2024, provide a broader focus on gender and diversity dimensions in research.

At global level, Science Europe, as co-chair of the EDI Working Group, organised a panel discussion during the annual GRC meeting on 'Promoting Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in Research – Reviewing the Statement of Principles after Seven Years', where participants from different world regions could share perspectives on how their institutions were promoting equality and inclusion.

2023 WOMEN IN SCIENCE CAMPAIGN

On the occasion of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, and International Women's Day, Science Europe once again celebrated the role of women in science. Between 11 February and 8 March, we put a spotlight on the contributions of leading women in our Empowering Women in Science campaign. María Cruz (NWO), Chair of the Working Group on Open Science; Carolina Cañibano (CSIC), Chair of the Working Group on Research Culture; Annely Allik (ETAG), Chair of the Working Group on Communication; Hannele Lahtinen, Chair of the Working Group on Horizon Europe; Krisztina Szepesvári, Chair of the Working Group on Horizon Europe; and Lidia Borrell-Damián, Science Europe Secretary General and Chair of the High Level Policy Network, all shared their personal experiences, career challenges, and perspectives on improving gender equality in research, inspiring the next generation of female leaders in research policy.

“By fostering an environment where all voices are heard, a richer, more robust research landscape will develop, allowing diverse societal challenges to be addressed more effectively.”

MELANIE WELHAM / EXECUTIVE CHAIR OF UK RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (UKRI)

#WomenInScienceDay

Watch our interviews sharing the experiences of female Science Europe Working Group Chairs on gender equality in science.

scienceeurope.org/news/empowering-women-in-science/

RESEARCH INTEGRITY AND ETHICS

Ensuring integrity and ethics in research practices is fundamental to fostering positive research cultures and driving meaningful shifts in shaping the future of research environments.

During 2023, Science Europe continued to contribute to the update of the [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#), managed by the [European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities \(ALLEA\)](#).

The revised Code incorporated many of the insights provided by Science Europe during the consultation process, placing a stronger emphasis on the roles and responsibilities of research organisations in upholding standards of ethics and integrity and fostering supportive research cultures, conducive to integrity. The adoption of more inclusive language acknowledged the diverse roles and contributions from individuals within research communities. It also expanded the scope of research outputs to explicitly include science communication and public engagement activities, reflecting the evolving landscape of research dissemination and underscoring the significance of transparent and ethical communication to build public trust.

Our input, together with the results of the [2022 High Level Workshop on Research Integrity and Ethics in the Context of Public Engagement](#) will form our contribution to the [World Conferences on Research Integrity](#) in June 2024.

“Integrity and ethics are at the heart of scientific progress, shaping research cultures and environments. Science Europe wholeheartedly supports the evolution of a set of global ethical standards, crucial for building public trust in science.”

FRANCISCO JAVIER MORENO FUENTES / VICE PRESIDENT FOR INTERNATIONAL AFFAIRS, SPANISH NATIONAL RESEARCH COUNCIL (CSIC)

Science Europe will contribute to 'The World Conferences on Research Integrity' in June 2024.

The publication 'The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity'.

OPEN SCIENCE

Science Europe has been at the forefront of collaborative efforts to unite the scientific research sector around common goals to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation, and communication as part of the development of well-functioning research systems.

Following the launch of the Action Plan for Diamond Open Access, the first Global Summit on Diamond Open Access was co-organised by Science Europe with global partners in Toluca, México, in October 2023. It was a significant milestone on the road towards a scholarly communication ecosystem made by researchers, with researchers, and for researchers. Bringing together nearly 700 people representing 457 institutions from 75 countries in North America, Latin America and the Caribbean, Africa, Europe, and Asia, this hybrid and multi-lingual gathering aimed to encourage a deeper understanding and mutual learning, and to share good practices, policies, and perspectives from around the world on the equity, quality, usability, and sustainability of this scholarly publishing model. The conclusions from the summit emphasised global engagement and exchange as the way forward.

The [2nd Diamond Open Access Conference](#), organised in the framework of the summit by Science Europe, [COALITION S](#), [OPERAS](#), and the [French National Research Agency \(ANR\)](#) brought together signatories to the

[Action Plan for Diamond Open Access](#) to further develop efficiency, quality standards, capacity building, and sustainability. It built on discussions at two community webinars that took place in April and September 2023.

Also in October, Science Europe also contributed to the third workshop in the series on 'Global Equity in Open Access Publishing,' organised by the OA2020 initiative to discuss practical mechanisms and action plans to remove barriers for readers and authors in the Americas, in the transition to an open and globally equitable research system. A Science Europe webinar in September explored the contribution of open research methods to developing a research culture based on open science, improving the quality of research overall.

A joint session of our Working Groups on Research Culture and Open Science in May on the establishment of assessment criteria for open science, acknowledged the interconnections between the two priorities. Reforming research assessment

practices holds the key to realising aspirations in the field of open science and research culture, as well as driving broader cultural transformations within the European research landscape and on a global scale. The joint session focused on mutual learning and knowledge exchange with members of both Working Groups considering ways to transform these insights into practical steps.

The adoption of national strategies on open science by several European governments, the launch of the [US Year on Open Science](#), the development of a [DIAMAS Diamond Capacity Hub](#) and [Global Alliance for Diamond Open Access](#), and the publication of [EU Council Conclusions on High Quality, Transparent, Open, Trustworthy, and Equitable Scholarly Publishing](#) demonstrate a growing momentum for change. The agreement by organisations attending the Global Summit to generate a worldwide federation of services in support of Diamond OA initiatives will provide added impetus during 2024 to build on these collective actions, to ensure equitable open access becomes a reality for all.

“Open science is the cornerstone of progress. The creation of an inclusive scholarly environment based on collaboration and dialogue, will drive innovation, inclusivity, and excellence in scientific research worldwide.”

THIERRY DAMERVAL / PRESIDENT/CEO OF THE FRENCH NATIONAL RESEARCH AGENCY (ANR)

scienceeurope.org/events/2023-global-summit-diamond-oa/

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/open-science

SHAPE EUROPEAN RESEARCH POLICY DEVELOPMENTS

THE SCIENCE EUROPE STRATEGY PLAN / 2021-2026

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS

Contributing to EU policy developments and legislation to support innovation and a strong research environment.

Fostering multi-lateral dialogues with non-EU countries, based on academic freedom, equity and reciprocity.

Developing a new framework for Science Europe members to evaluate the effectiveness of their cross-border initiatives.

EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA

The European Research Area (ERA) aims to create a single, borderless market for research, innovation and technology across the EU. Science Europe continues to support its members to drive the development of ERA policies to build the strongest possible research ecosystem for the benefit of science, researchers, and society.

During 2023, as part of our ongoing commitment to shaping the future of research and innovation in Europe, Science Europe actively participated in several crucial workshops and meetings focused on the implementation and evaluation of the ERA's current policy agenda (2021–2024).

As well as continuing to advocate policies that foster innovation, address emerging challenges, and promote diversity and inclusion, in meetings of the ERA Forum and its sub-groups, we contributed to the development of the [Framework on Research Careers](#), and offered insights on issues such as gender-based violence and harassment in research; the [EU Science](#)

[Diplomacy Agenda](#); addressing foreign interference; and fostering multilateral dialogues with non-EU countries. The latter was also the theme of the [15th High Level Workshop on the ERA](#), in Madrid, Spain, on 29 and 30 November (see the section International Collaboration on p.25 for more information). We were also a key participant in the kick-off meeting on the ERA Action aiming to enhance the strategic capacity of Europe's public research performing organisations.

Science Europe will continue to actively participate in the reflection process on priorities and definition of the ERA Policy Agenda 2025–2027.

We will follow the process closely, stressing the importance of maintaining focus on essential priorities such as reform of research assessment, research careers, Open Science, ethics and integrity, international collaboration, and equality, diversity, and inclusion. We will also continue to champion strong connections between the ERA Policy Agenda and the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, shaping policies that empower researchers and contribute to societal progress.

“The European Research Area is pivotal for nurturing collaboration and innovation across the EU, building a robust research ecosystem, benefitting science, researchers, and society as a whole.”

ADRIAN CURAJ / DIRECTOR GENERAL OF THE EXECUTIVE AGENCY FOR HIGHER EDUCATION, RESEARCH, DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION FUNDING OF ROMANIA (UEFISCDI)

EU FRAMEWORK PROGRAMMES HORIZON EUROPE

The European Framework Programmes for Research and Innovation (R&I) are crucial instruments to boost European scientific excellence, facilitate collaboration among the European R&I communities, and further develop the European Research Area. In 2023, Science Europe and its members have actively contributed to reflections on the past, present, and future editions of the programme, as discussions on the successor to Horizon Europe began.

The year 2023 provided an opportunity to take stock of Science Europe members' experiences of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe. We collected their initial perspectives on the next strategic plan for 2025–2027 (and future programmes more broadly) and provided these in a response to a public consultation organised by the European Commission.

The lack of adequate funding continues to be a key concern, with the current programme only being able to fund 19% of the high-quality proposals it receives. In October, we called on the European Council to reverse proposed cuts to the 2024 budget that jeopardise the implementation of ambitious R&I policies, as well as to ring-fence funding for the 2025–2027 strategic plan to protect the future budget.

As emphasis shifts in the objectives of the Framework Programmes towards the prioritisation of rapid economic impact, Science Europe took the opportunity to advocate, in its response to the consultation, a better balance between fundamental and applied research and more inclusion of social sciences and the humanities to ensure that societal challenges are adequately addressed. The evolving geopolitical landscape, particularly the conflict in Ukraine and shifting relations with countries like China, also poses challenges that Horizon Europe could address. Our members, welcoming policy developments such as the reform of research assessment, also highlighted the need to prioritise reducing disparities in R&I capacity across Europe and address challenges in the implementation and administrative procedures – especially concerning the complexity of partnerships and missions.

In September, Science Europe applauded the agreement on the participation of the United Kingdom in the Horizon Europe and Copernicus programmes, following the UK's departure from the EU.

Together with our members, we strongly support the *Stick to Science* initiative, which calls for an open, inclusive, and excellence-driven European Research Area. It continues to advocate a renewed association agreement with Switzerland, which has been outside the programme since 2021.

“Horizon Europe plays a vital role in advancing European scientific excellence and collaboration, essential for building a strong European Research Area.”

MARI SUNDLI TVEIT / CHIEF EXECUTIVE OF THE RESEARCH COUNCIL OF NORWAY (RCN)

The publication 'Public Consultation on Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe'.

scienceeurope.org/our-resources/science-europe-response-to-the-public-consultation-on-horizon-2020-and-horizon-europe/

EU LEGISLATION

At the core of Science Europe’s activities is our commitment to championing the perspectives and viewpoints of our members and safeguarding the collective interests of our membership. As a critical ally of the EU, we are a trusted and dependable partner, contributing to the achievement of mutual goals and objectives.

Science Europe aims to ensure that the interests of the research community are effectively represented in policy discussions and the evolution of legislative proposals at European level, engaging with policy makers to address emerging issues to foster innovation, protect academic freedom, and promote international collaboration.

We continued to highlight the serious concerns for research and innovation from European legislation on data and digital issues, in workshops that took place in February 2023. These allowed our members to share their experiences of the impact of existing legislation on research, and to explore potential corrective measures. A clear takeaway from the discussion was that the pluralism of national rules and exemptions that has emerged, creates uncertainty for the inherently international research sector. More EU alignment was considered a key priority by participants.

In July, in response to calls for legislation to end all animal testing in the EU by June 2024, Science Europe, while supporting the highest possible welfare and ethical standards, joined members of the scientific community in calling for caution and nuance in discussions surrounding the phasing out of animal use in research. We also provided input to the revision of the EU Financial Regulation that sets the rules for all EU funding programmes; we supported in particular the possibility to allow unspent funds to be reinvested in their original headings.

We also contributed to a legislative proposal from the European Parliament that called for common rules and standards on the freedom of scientific research across Europe, which was voted on by MEPs in January 2024. While welcoming the initiative to reinforce protections for researchers, we also highlighted the need to avoid unintended consequences that may impact funding priorities and international collaboration.

“EU legislation profoundly shapes the European research landscape, impacting funding, collaboration, and innovation. It is crucial that it addresses emerging challenges to advance scientific endeavour.”

MARCEL LEVI / PRESIDENT OF THE DUTCH RESEARCH COUNCIL (NWO)

The Science Europe statement on animal use in research called for caution and nuance in discussions about its future.

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/eu-legislation

INTERNATIONAL CO-OPERATION

Science Europe continued to contribute to the development of international dialogue through the Global Research Council and the United Nations. It also supported its members to address challenges and facilitate impactful partnerships to foster international collaboration in research and innovation.

Our long-term strategy to support our members to develop fruitful international co-operations based on equitable and reciprocal approaches, the highest ethical standards, academic freedom, and human rights, was advanced during 2023 through a range of approaches.

Our flagship [High Level Workshop](#) in November was the culmination of a series of discussions throughout the year on the challenges and new mechanisms and policies that should be incorporated into European strategies to address the critical issues emerging in international research collaboration. It was also an opportunity to debate the tools, such as funding and measures to promote mobility, that underpin the development of stronger scientific collaboration networks.

A new framework for members to evaluate the outcomes of their cross-border initiatives was developed, facilitating a deeper understanding of the effectiveness of their efforts to develop international partnerships.

We continued to closely follow the [EU Multilateral Dialogue on Principles and Values for International Cooperation in Research and Innovation](#). This engagement included our contribution to a [Ministerial Statement](#), published under the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the EU in February 2024. This dialogue aims, through open discussion, to develop a shared understanding of the principles and values essential for international research and innovation co-operation.

15TH HIGH-LEVEL WORKSHOP ON THE ERA

Co-organised by Science Europe, the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), and the Spanish Ministry for Science, Innovation, and Universities (MCIU), the [15th High Level Workshop on the ERA](#) took place in Madrid on 29 and 30 November. It dealt with the themes of challenges for reciprocity in scientific collaboration between Europe, Africa, Latin America, and the Caribbean, academic freedom, and the role of global scientific networks in achieving positive change. This event also included a satellite workshop for researchers, tackling topics such as cultural heritage in R&I co-operation

and scientific collaboration in building sustainable value chains in raw materials. This showed the added value of international co-operation in terms of creating a critical mass of knowledge, fostering interdisciplinarity, and building long-term partnerships on shared values. A [statement](#) issued on the conclusion of the workshop reiterated the importance of international collaboration in research and innovation, calling on the European institutions, national governments, and research organisations to adopt a series of measures to develop mutually beneficial collaborations in the future.

[Watch the conference video](#)

[Read the conference report](#)

“International co-operation in science is vital to address global challenges and advance the pursuit of scholarly knowledge. Through continued dialogue, we can build strong networks and promote equitable, rights-based collaboration worldwide.”

FRANCISCO JAVIER MORENO FUENTES / VICE PRESIDENT FOR INTERNATIONAL AFFAIRS, SPANISH NATIONAL RESEARCH COUNCIL (CSIC)

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/cross-border-collaboration

INTERNATIONAL CO-OPERATION

(Continued)

TALKING SCIENCE CAMPAIGN: FOSTERING INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION

To further amplify the importance of international scientific collaboration, Science Europe launched the campaign 'Talking Science: Fostering International Collaboration' in the lead-up to the 15th High Level Workshop. It showcased the initiatives undertaken by Science Europe Member Organisations in collaboration with partners in Europe, Africa, Latin America, and the Caribbean. By highlighting successful collaborations and sharing best practices, Science Europe aimed to inspire mutual learning and promote the values of academic freedom, integrity, and reciprocity.

PARTICIPATION IN THE UN GENERAL ASSEMBLY SCIENCE SUMMIT

Our active participation in the [Science Summit at the 78th session of the United Nations General Assembly](#) underscored our commitment to global collaboration for sustainable development. Science Europe contributed with an introductory speech at the opening ceremony and a panel discussion on the '100 Days Mission', which aims to make safe and efficient vaccines

available around the world within 100 days, in the event of another pandemic. Science Europe also organised an online discussion on the need to ensure equitable access to global research data and how the development of FAIR research data spaces could be used to foster improved outcomes for sustainable development.

COLLABORATION WITH THE NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION OF CHINA

Avenues of co-operation with the [National Natural Science Foundation of China \(NSFC\)](#) continued to be explored. In 2023, discussions focused on data sharing and on identifying challenges and possible solutions (within the respective regulatory context) to the practical problems European researchers and organisations face when working with Chinese organisations. These are being followed up with further online discussions on the issue and an in-person meeting between the governance of Science Europe and the NSFC in the autumn of 2024.

GLOBAL RESEARCH COUNCIL

Acknowledging the contributions of researchers and devising equitable systems to recognise their efforts was one of the

main topics of deliberation at the 2023 Annual Meeting of the [Global Research Council \(GRC\)](#), co-organised by Science Europe member the [Dutch Research Council \(NWO\)](#). Together with the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#), Science Europe organised a side-event on the global dimension of research assessment reform across all five GRC regions. These discussions culminated in the adoption of a statement of principles identifying how research organisations might address the challenges involved in moving to new methods of research assessment.

The GRC European Regional Meeting took place on 20 and 21 November in Bucharest, Romania. Co-organised with the [Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development, and Innovation Funding of Romania \(UEFISCDI\)](#), discussions centred on the theme of 'sustainable research'. Insights were collected on the role of research in sustainable development, on ensuring the sustainability of research practices, and on promoting the relevance of sustainability science. These insights were used to inform European contributions at the GRC Annual Meeting in May 2024.

The 'Talking Science' campaign showcased our members' initiatives to promote international collaboration.

Science Europe's participation at the 2023 UN Science Summit underscored our commitment to global collaboration for sustainable development.

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

As the research infrastructure landscape continues to evolve, Science Europe remains a key advocate for fostering international collaboration and advancing strategic considerations to support the establishment and operation of research infrastructures of all types and sizes. Our ongoing partnership with the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development's Global Science Forum (OECD-GSF) underscores our commitment to supporting the development of research infrastructures on a global scale.

Very Large Research Infrastructures (VLRIs), characterised by their complexity and international dimension, play a pivotal role in driving cutting-edge research across diverse domains. During 2023, we continued to take part in the OECD Expert Group on VLRIs, which published a policy paper in July, providing a synthesis of the insights from workshops, surveys, and case studies. It presented perspectives and good practice examples from a number of Science Europe members (RCN, VR, UKRI, and NWO), and a series of lessons learned regarding the establishment of VLRIs; options for improving their use and operation; as well as more strategic considerations that VLRI managers, funders, and decision makers should take into account.

As part of our priority to encourage international collaboration and recognise the role of national research infrastructures as part of the global research infrastructure landscape, Science Europe also launched a new project with OECD-GSF in 2023 looking at the interaction between national and international funding for – and collaboration between – RIs. A workshop for our members in 2024 will provide input to and discuss the initial findings of this project.

Research infrastructures are also an important consideration for the development of the European Research Area. In April 2023, as part of the [European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures \(ESFRI\) Stakeholder Forum](#), Science Europe provided strategic input to a consultation on the development of the next ESFRI Roadmap. This will focus on the role and importance of nationally funded and nationally operated RIs in an international context, and the role that RIs play as part of the Open Science movement.

We also contributed to first ideas for the drafting of an update to the [European Charter of Access to Research Infrastructures](#) and spoke on the topic at the 2nd ESFRI Stakeholder Forum meeting in September 2023.

“Frontier research relies on strong research infrastructures. Only through ongoing collaboration can we build the necessary foundations to foster continued scientific progress and innovation.”

MARCEL LEVI / PRESIDENT OF THE DUTCH RESEARCH COUNCIL (NWO)

Science Europe and a number of our members contributed to the OECD policy paper on VLRIs in July.

Science Europe attended the ESFRI Stakeholder Forum meeting in September.

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/research-infrastructures

STRENGTHEN THE ROLE AND CONTRIBUTION OF SCIENCE IN TACKLING SOCIETAL CHALLENGES

THE SCIENCE EUROPE STRATEGY PLAN / 2021-2026

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS

Promoting science-informed decision-making to support policymakers in tackling societal issues and advancing sustainable development.

Exploring the potential and challenges posed by AI tools in science.

Developing a roadmap to build connections between researchers and society, including planning for a high-level conference on science communication in 2024.

THE GREEN AND DIGITAL TRANSITION

Scientific research can and should support policy makers in navigating how to tackle the complex challenges society faces such as climate change. The complex, bi-directional exchanges between decision making and research communities require trust, commitment, and collective engagement, which is particularly challenging in a context of distrust, misinformation and fake news. 2023 saw the publication of a landmark report to support science-informed policy making to leverage research to address societal challenges and drive sustainable development.

A high-level event featuring Marc Lemaître, the European Commission's newly appointed Director-General for Research and Innovation, marked the launch of our report '[Science-Policy in Action: Insights for the Green and Digital Transition](#)'. Mapping activities, strategies, and examples of science-policy interfaces in this context, the report identified three models of interaction: from policy makers to researchers, from researchers to policy makers, and structured science-policy hubs that facilitate bi-directional exchanges. While focusing on the policy areas of climate and digitalisation, the findings underscore the relevance of science-policy interfaces across all policy fields, advocating concerted efforts to promote interdisciplinary dialogue and evidence-based decision making.

In April, Science Europe launched the follow-up report to a symposium held in November 2022 together with CESAER, the International Sustainable Campus Network (ISCN), and the University of Strathclyde, ahead of COP27. Entitled '[Interdisciplinarity for the Net-Zero Transition](#)', the report highlights the actions being taken by universities and research organisations to 'green' their activities and promote climate actions. It aims to inspire other research organisations to join efforts to more effectively and rapidly address the climate crisis.

In October, we began the development of a framework on the 'greening' of research activities. This framework aims to identify priorities, areas of interest, and fields to develop and upgrade joint actions for making science itself sustainable, aligning with one of the 2023-2024 priorities of the Global Research Council.

Following on from these key reports, Science Europe developed [practical guidelines](#) for research organisations to contribute to science-informed policy making (published in 2024). We also aim to identify and learn from our members who are already taking steps to appraise and minimise their carbon footprint and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Their findings will be used to develop guidance for research organisations to take actionable steps to towards achieving climate sustainability and a greener future.

"Science, underpinned by interdisciplinary dialogue and evidence-based policy making, holds the key to navigating complex societal challenges, such as climate change."

MARC SCHILTZ / SECRETARY GENERAL OF THE LUXEMBOURG NATIONAL RESEARCH FUND (FNR)

Marc Lemaître,
DG for Research
and Innovation,
European Commission,
at the launch of our
report on supporting
science-policy
interfaces.

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/green-and-digital-transition

SCIENCE COMMUNICATION

Effective science communication is an integral pillar for fostering understanding, engagement, and societal impact; not only to showcase the value of research investment in addressing collective challenges, but also to improve our understanding of the research process itself.

Building on its 2022 Position Statement, Science Communication for Greater Research Impact, Science Europe continued to work with its members to strengthen their capacity and support their efforts to communicate research more effectively.

Through both online and in-person meetings of the Working Group on Communication, we created opportunities to identify the latest trends, share best practices, foster dialogue on how we can collectively improve science communication, and chart a roadmap with concrete actions to amplify the voice of science and bridge the gap between researchers and society. These sessions not only facilitated the showcasing of innovative science communication initiatives, but also paved the way for fruitful collaborations, including engagement with [COALESCE](#), a project dedicated to establishing a European Competence Centre for Science Communication.

Looking forward to March 2024, Science Europe also developed plans for a [High Level Conference on Science Communication](#), co-organised with the [Research Foundation Flanders \(FWO\)](#) and the [National Fund for Scientific Research \(FNRS\)](#), under the auspices of the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the EU. An ambitious programme bringing together European and national policy makers, heads of research organisations, academics, communications professionals, and the media aimed to underscore the critical importance of science communication in shaping research narratives and fostering societal engagement.

The formulation of a comprehensive Communications Roadmap and the launch of targeted campaigns such as [#TalkingScience](#) (to showcase how our members uphold high ethics and integrity standards in their public engagement projects) and [#WomenInScience](#) (highlighting the experiences of women who have achieved senior positions in research) are some of our other activities contributing to our broader objective of strengthening the voice of science in and for society.

“Effective science communication is essential for bridging the gap between research and society, and foster understanding, engagement, and informed decision making.”

ANTONIO ZOCCOLI / PRESIDENT OF THE NATIONAL INSTITUTE FOR NUCLEAR PHYSICS (INFN)

High Level Conference on Science Communication.

scienceeurope.org/events/high-level-conference-science-communication/

Empowering Women in Science campaign.

scienceeurope.org/news/empowering-women-in-science/

Talking Science Campaign on International Collaboration.

scienceeurope.org/news/talking-science-fostering-international-collaboration-campaign-launch

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/science-communication

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications show great potential to create far-reaching changes in all parts of the research process. Science Europe has embarked on several initiatives and collaborations to support our members to understand, harness, and responsibly navigate the landscape of AI in research.

In response to the rapid development and growing use of AI, we launched a first workshop in September 2023 with our members to explore both the potential of and challenges posed by AI tools in research. While AI-based tools offer immense potential, they also present challenges – notably, ensuring data reproducibility and integrity, and researchers' responsible use of the technology.

Recognising the need for guidance on the responsible use of AI for research activities, Science Europe has begun initiatives to support RFOs' and RPOs' responsible uptake of AI tools with best practice guidelines, knowledge sharing among members, and the development of fit-for-purpose infrastructure.

At the same time, we have actively engaged in European Commission-led initiatives, such as the Task Force on Generative AI (GenAI), which aims to develop [European guidance on the responsible use of AI in research](#).

These efforts represent a significant step towards fostering a Europe-wide discussion on the ethical use of AI, from the perspective of both research funding and research performing organisations. Science Europe will continue to closely follow and contribute to such developments in 2024.

“The potential of Artificial Intelligence to transform research processes and ecosystems, means that Science Europe’s support to navigate this new landscape is crucial.”

ANGELIKA KALT / DIRECTOR OF THE SWISS NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION (SNSF)

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/eu-legislation/artificial-intelligence

AFTERWORD

2023 proved to be another landmark year for Science Europe: building on the achievements of the previous year and setting the direction for new approaches in vital areas of research policy.

The growing interest in the reform of research assessment, following the launch of the [Coalition for the Reform of Research Assessment](#) in December 2022, has been a major development in efforts to transform research culture. Over 600 organisations, including the majority of Science Europe members, are now part of this global coalition, with its own working groups and national chapters, committed to developing a shared approach to changes in research assessment to maximise the quality and impact of research. At the same time, the first [Global Summit on Diamond Open Access](#) set in motion the creation of a global movement to develop common goals to open the creation, evaluation, and communication of scientific knowledge. Together with our input to an updated [European Code of Conduct on Research Integrity](#) and the preparation of renewed [guidance](#) on improving equality, diversity and inclusion, we aim to support our members to implement a positive culture where research and researchers can thrive.

We had crucial conversations with our members and partners on how we can ensure an ambitious budget for research and innovation, bolster international collaboration, or tackle the gaps in

investment across the EU, as discussions continued on the priorities of the European Research Area and the reflection process on past, current, and future funding programmes got underway. Science Europe pledges to continue to raise these important issues in 2024 as the European Parliament and Commission renew their mandate and set the legislative agenda for the coming five years including a [campaign](#) (at current time of writing) on the importance of European research and innovation.

We remain resolute in our support for the National Research Foundation of Ukraine as a valued member of the international research community. Our participation in the [UN Science Summit](#) and organisation of the [High Level Workshop](#) were opportunities to focus on the benefits of international co-operation and building partnerships based on equity and reciprocity to tackle common global societal challenges, themes we will also continue to explore during 2024.

A personal highlight was the publication of our landmark [report](#) to support science-informed policy making, outlining our members' current strategies on science-policy interfaces and how researchers can improve the way which emphasised the importance of interdisciplinary dialogue and evidence-based decision making. We will continue to support our members to work with policy makers with the publication of [guidance](#) on science for policy activities in 2024,

based on the findings of the report. Another focus of our activities during 2023 was the planning for our [High-Level Conference on Science Communication](#), one of the priorities of the 2024 Belgian Presidency of the EU, on the importance of science communication in research processes and systems and how we can tackle mis- and disinformation and better engage the public in the dialogue between research and society. Together with our members, we are also following closely the emergence of Artificial Intelligence, the implications of its use in research systems and processes, and how it can be harnessed ethically and effectively to enhance scientific research and innovation.

On behalf of my colleagues in the Science Europe Office, I would like to welcome our new President, Mari Sundli Tveit, who will lead our efforts to promote knowledge-sharing, collaboration and the advancement of common interests and priorities to build a stronger research environment. I know we can rely on our members' continuing interest and engagement in our activities, and the diverse perspectives they bring, to enhance our collective efforts to foster a collaborative research landscape that drives progress and addresses the complex challenges facing our world.

LIDIA BORRELL-DAMIÁN / SECRETARY GENERAL OF SCIENCE EUROPE

“Our activities during 2023 reinforced our commitment to improving research systems and processes. We pledge to sustain these vital conversations and initiatives, to continue to support a thriving research environment.”

ANNEX

GOVERNING BOARD MEMBERS 2021-2023

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Marc Schiltz <i>(President)</i>	Secretary General of the Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Angelika Kalt <i>(Vice-President representing RFOs)</i>	Director of the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Marcel Levi <i>(Vice-President representing RPOs)</i>	President of the Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Francisco Javier Moreno Fuentes	Vice-President for International Affairs, Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Adrian Curaj	Director General of the Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Thierry Damerval	President/CEO of the French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Matthias Koenig	Vice-President of the German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Mari Sundli Tveit	Chief Executive of the Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Melanie Welham	Executive Chair of the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Antonio Zoccoli	President of the National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy

GOVERNING BOARD MEMBERS ELECTED NOVEMBER 2023

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Mari Sundli Tveit <i>(President)</i>	Chief Executive of the Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Francisco Javier Moreno Fuentes <i>(Vice-President representing RPOs)</i>	Vice-President for International Affairs, Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Marcel Levi <i>(Vice-President representing RFOs)</i>	President of the Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Katarina Bjelke	Director General of the Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Adrian Curaj	Director General of the Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Anna Di Ciaccio	Director of the National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Milica Đurić-Jovičić	Acting Director of the Science Fund of the Republic Of Serbia (SFRS)	Serbia
Christof Gattringer	President of the Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Matthias Koenig	Vice-President of the German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Christopher Smith	Executive Chair of the Arts and Humanities Research Council, UK Research & Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

OVERVIEW OF 2023 WORKING GROUPS AND TASK FORCES

HIGH-LEVEL POLICY NETWORK ON THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA AND CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY	NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Abillis, Gregory	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium	Mico Egea, Victoria	United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Bak, Sebastiaan den	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands	Mistrík, Robert	Slovak Research and Development Agency (APVV)	Slovakia
Bärenreuter, Christoph	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria	Mortensen, Jakob Nedergaard	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFP)	Denmark
Bell, Linda	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden	Muižniece, Lauma	Latvian Council of Science (LZP)	Latvia
Belocky, Reinhard	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria	Nieto Garcia, Maria Cristina	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Berndt, Anja	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom	Noorma, Anu	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Boc, Mojca	Slovenian Research Agency (ARRS)	Slovenia	Ognois, Laure	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Boehme, Olivier	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium	Pětrašová, Kamila	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Boljević, Jasminka	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia	Pin, Pierre-Olivier	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Bondre-Beil, Priya	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany	Plewinska, Honorata	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Butt, Dominique (Until July)	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom	Poll, Myriam	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Chioncel, Mariana	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI)	Romania	Polotska, Olga	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Curaj, Adrian	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI)	Romania	Rebhan, Christian	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Danielsen, Kristin	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway	Sara-Kennedy, Rachael	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Doménech, Elena	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain	Štomińska, Kinga	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland
Domínguez, Elena	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain	Tejada, Laura	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Dunon-Bluteau, Dominique	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France	Törnqvist, Stefan	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Đurić-Jovičić, Milica	Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia (SFRS)	Serbia	Verbaeys, Isabelle	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Fängström, Britta	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden	Vistad, Rune	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Folea, Antoaneta	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research Development and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI)	Romania	Wachter, Wolfgang	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Groeneveld, Joël	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium	Wiley, Paul	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Hakala, Johanna	Academy of Finland (AKA)	Finland	Woźniakowska, Justyna	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Hansteen, Thomas	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway	Zagalo Pereira, Gonçalo	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Horst, Maja (Until June)	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFP)	Denmark	Zondaka, Elita	Latvian Council of Science (LZP)	Latvia
Kuipers, Joyce	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands			
Marti, Simon	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland			
Martinović Klarić, Irena	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia			

CHAIRS

Borrell-Damián, Lidia (Chair HLPN on ERA)**Burg, Helena** (Chair HLPN on CBC) Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR) Luxembourg

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Braem, Adrien (ERA) **Lemahieu, Sophie** (CBC)

MEMBERS OF THE TASK FORCE ON MONITORING CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Absillis, Gregory	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Belocky, Reinhard	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Lecic, Dario	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Burg, Helena	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Butt, Dominique	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Lee, Natasha	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Telford, Myriam	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Muppavarapu, Vydehi	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Jakobs, Tom	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Łazarowicz-Kowalik, Marta	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland
Martínez, Catalina	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Martin-Lanuza, Monica	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Plewinska, Honorata	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Neouze, Maïa	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Repnik, Robert	Slovenian Research Agency (ARRS)	Slovenia
Strzebońska, Anna	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Učakar Petrovčič, Lucija	Slovenian Research Agency (ARRS)	Slovenia
Virlon, Bérangère	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Vodjdani, Nakita	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Wojciechowska, Paulina	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
CO-CHAIRS		
Dinkel, William	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Tejada, Laura	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland

MEMBERS OF THE TASK FORCE ON CHINA

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Bain, Magnus	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Bak, Sebastiaan den	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Bondre-Beil, Priya	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Bonenkamp, Berry	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Durrans, Sophie	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Grasso, Simona	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Hansteen, Thomas	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Krűßmann, Ingrid	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Kuipers, Joyce	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Pin, Pierre-Olivier	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Schlepper, Gerrit Andreas	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Wachter, Wolfgang	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Wiley, Paul	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

MEMBERS OF THE WORKING GROUP ON HORIZON EUROPE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ancāns, Jānis	Latvian Council of Science (LZP)	Latvia
Belocky, Reinhard	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Boljević, Jasminka	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Brookes, Jonathan	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Bühler, Sarah	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Devine, Ellenor	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Doménech, Elena	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Fängström, Britta	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Herranz Cecilia, Aida	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Kazai, Zsolt	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Kostka, Sylwia	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Kotarba, Anna	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Kuipers, Joyce	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Miller, Christina	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Møller, Tom-Espen	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Mortensen, Jakob Nedergaard	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFP)	Denmark
Mortensen, Maria	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFP)	Denmark
Munhá, Rui	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Nakath, Richard	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Nash, Maria	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Oitmaa, Kristel	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Pin, Pierre-Olivier	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Polotska, Olga	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Rodríguez, Cristina	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Serrano, Joaquín	Spanish State Research Agency (AEI)	Spain
Simion, Elena	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Szendrey, Adrienn	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Totland, Karin	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Van Hauwaert, Ann	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Vistad, Rune	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Winger, Martin	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Wittorski, Natacha	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
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Lahtinen, Hannele	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Szepesvári, Krisztina	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:		
Lemahieu, Sophie		

MEMBERS OF THE WORKING GROUP ON OPEN SCIENCE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
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Bolliger, Isabel	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
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Galica, Natalia	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Garnier, Martine	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Garrido, Julián	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
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Halling, Sanja	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Hautala, Harri	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Irimia, Alina	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Jakobs, Tom	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Kita, Jean-Claude	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
Kokorevičs, Arnis	Latvian Science Council (LZP)	Latvia
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Meeus, Joke	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
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Piirsoo, Marko	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Podolieva, Alina	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Ponsati, Agnes	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Primo, Elena	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Pristovšek, Primož	Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS)	Slovenia
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Robotka, Balázs	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Rosendahl, Lasse Aistrup	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFP)	Denmark
Winkler, Kathrin <i>(Until August)</i>	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Wojtyra, Wiktorja	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland

CHAIR

Cruz, Maria	Dutch Research Council, (NWO)	Netherlands
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SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Saenen, Bregt

MEMBERS OF THE TASK FORCE ON OPEN RESEARCH SOFTWARE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ancion, Zoé	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Boccali, Tommaso	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Cruz, Maria	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Karcher, Stefan	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Katerbow, Matthias	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Martinez Ortiz, Carlos	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Perez, Daniel	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Popa, Andreea	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Rieck, Katharina	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Spanache, Ioana	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania

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NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Baltzrud, Lillian M.	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Boehme, Olivier	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Bolliger, Isabel	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Chiarelli, Giorgio	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Cody, Anne	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Costa, Rosário	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Gayoso, Pilar	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Gossink, Kasper	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Grainger, Kirsty (<i>until September</i>)	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Grimm, Tobias	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Guyard, Laurence	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Györfi, Miklós	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Holliday, Linda	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Holm, Jon	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Juurik, Marten	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Kokorevičs, Arnis	Latvian Science Council (LZP)	Latvia
Kolotilov, Sergey	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Lachat, Fanny	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Łazarowicz-Kowalik, Marta	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland
Martinović Klarić, Irena	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
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Olsson, Emma	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Rieck, Katharina	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Sánchez, Irene	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Schiøtt, Birgit	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFP)	Denmark
Ségérie, Audrey	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
Sigurðsson, Sigurður Óli	Icelandic Centre for Research (Rannís)	Iceland

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Söderlind, Johan	Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare (FORTE)	Sweden
Spanache, Ioana	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Steinczinger, Zsuzsanna	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Stevanovic, Ana	Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia (SFRS)	Serbia
Strinzel, Michaela	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Szymańska-Skolimowska, Ewelina	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Valosaari, Kata-Riina	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland

CO-CHAIRS

Cañibano, Carolina	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Sapcariu, Sean	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Morris, James

MEMBERS OF THE TASK FORCE ON RECOGNITION SYSTEMS

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Cahill, Aoife	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
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Grimm, Tobias	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Lund, Christian	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
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Milovanović Soldatić, Sandra	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Ošo, Simon	Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS)	Slovenia
Reynolds, Abigail	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Sapcariu, Sean	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Spanache, Ioana	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania

MEMBERS OF THE TASK FORCE ON RESEARCH CAREERS

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Baltzrud, Lillian	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Buckow, Anjana	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Cañibano, Carolina	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Chiarelli, Giorgio	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Costa, Rosário	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Olsson, Emma	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Sapcariu, Sean	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Schiøtt, Birgit	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
Ségerie, Audrey	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
Szymańska-Skolimowska, Ewelina	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Valosaari, Kata-Riina	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Van Acker, Frederik	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium

MEMBERS OF THE TASK FORCE ON EQUALITY, DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Cañibano, Carolina	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Chiarelli, Giorgio	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Costa, Rosário	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Fritch, Rochelle	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Isala, Ana	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Jonsson, Inger	Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare (FORTE)	Sweden
Lorenzini, Jasmine	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Mik-Meyer, Nanna	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
O'Leary, Jo	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Reichwein, Eva	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Szymańska-Skolimowska, Ewelina	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Thijs, Tim	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Wampach, Linda	National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Westholm, Lisa	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden

MEMBERS OF THE TASK FORCE ON RESEARCH INTEGRITY

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Boehme, Olivier	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Boland, Marion	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Kolu, Päivi	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Lachat, Fanny	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Montoliu, Lluís	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Ottinger, Teresa	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Rouby, Asael	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Steinberger, Martin	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Szymańska-Skolimowska, Ewelina	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Veitch, Rebecca	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

MEMBERS OF THE WORKING GROUP ON THE GREEN AND DIGITAL TRANSITION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Achermann, Sarah	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Aït-Ameur, Yamine	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Clarke, Patricia	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Del Río González, Pablo	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Diaz, Julio	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Ferre, Marian	Spanish State Research Agency (AEI)	Spain
Heylen, Steven	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Imrik, Krisztina	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Jarecka-Stepień, Katarzyna	National Science Center (NCN)	Poland
Joerk, Christiane	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Kaell, Christiane	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Klobučar, Marko	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Leskinen, Paula	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Lorentzen, Philip	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Martín, Fernando	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Prado, Margarida	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Prieur-Richard, Anne-Hélène	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Ryan, Michael	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Simion, Elena	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Stuefer, Josef	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Teschke, Meike	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Thoonen, Guy	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Verbovszky, Gabriella	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Webb, Sarah	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
CHAIR <i>(until December 23)</i>		
Mobjörk, Malin	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:		
Dotti, Nicola Francesco		

MEMBERS OF THE TASK FORCE ON GUIDANCE FOR SCIENCE-POLICY INTERFACES

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Aït-Ameur, Yamine	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Clarke, Patricia	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Prado, Margarida	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Stuefer, Josef	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Verbovszky, Gabriella	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
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Mobjörk, Malin	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden

MEMBERS OF THE TASK FORCE GREENING RESEARCH ORGANISATIONS

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Achermann, Sarah	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Del Río González, Pablo	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Imrik, Krisztina	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Heylen, Steven	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Kaell, Christiane	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
O'Brien, Shona	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Prieur-Richard, Anne-Hélène	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Simion, Elena	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Stuefer, Josef	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Thoonen, Guy	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Verbovszky, Gabriella	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Winkler, Amelie	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany

MEMBERS OF THE WORKING GROUP ON COMMUNICATION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ármannsson, Davið Fjólnir	Icelandic Centre for Research (Rannís)	Iceland
Barbé, Kim	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Bastong, Benedikt	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Bilyi, Oleksandr	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Blomberg, Elisabet	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Chorošenin, Petr	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Courant, Marion	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Delvax, Liesbeth	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Aksjonova, Darja (from September)	Latvian Science Council (LZP)	Latvia
Dūša, Laura (until September)	Latvian Science Council (LZP)	Latvia
Ekelöf, Sia	Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life & Welfare (FORTE)	Sweden
Evensen, Thomas	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Ferreira, Luís	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Ferreira, Joana	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Fleetwood, Anna Maria	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Fülöp, Emese Andrea	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Futrell, Jane	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
García Gonzalo, Marta	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Ginic, Natalija	Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia (SFRS)	Serbia
Goossens, Didier	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Grau, Abel	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Harket, Hilde Totland	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Hoekstra, Ynte	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Houssein, Sherylee	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Imperiali, Fabrice	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Janů, Vojtěch	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Korzekwa-Józefowicz, Anna	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Kranewitter, Stefan	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Le Floch, Katel	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Lečić, Dario	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Machulina, Tetiana	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Markey, Gillian	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Michalska-Bugajska, Marta	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland
Niil, Christian	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
O'Driscoll, Lorna	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Ólafsson, Alda	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Ortega, Inés	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Plaza, Jose Antonio	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Rotar, Adriana	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Sarbach, Jun	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Thuvesson, Zandra	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Tuetey, Stéphanie	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
Varaschin, Antonella	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Winnen, Eric	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
CHAIR		
Allik, Annelly (Chair)	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Garoia, Valentina

SCIENCE EUROPE STAFF MEMBERS 2023

NAME	TITLE
Lidia Borrell-Damián	Secretary General Since September 2019
Adrien Braem	Senior Policy Officer Since October 2017
Sara Cesari	Policy Officer Since March 2022
Nicola Francesco Dotti	Senior Policy Officer Until June 2024
Riccardo Durante	Administrative Assistant Until April 2024
Stéphanie Flouquet	Personal and Administrative Assistant Since March 2021
Valentina Garoia	Communications Manager Until September 2023
Iwan Groeneveld	Communications and Events Officer Since June 2015
Alexander Halksworth	Communications Officer Since September 2023
James Morris	Senior Policy Officer Since July 2019

NAME	TITLE
Justine Moynat	Junior Communications Officer Until July 2023
Mathilde Reumaux	Senior Policy Officer Until March 2023
Artemis Rodopoulou	Office Manager Since August 2013
Bregt Saenen	Senior Policy Officer Since November 2021
Claire Salinas	Senior Policy Officer Until May 2024

SCIENCE EUROPE PUBLICATIONS 2023

TITLE	PUBLICATION DATE
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ERA AND HORIZON EUROPE

Science Europe Response to the Public Consultation on Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe	February
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GREEN AND DIGITAL TRANSITION

Science-Policy in Action: Insights for the Green and Digital Transition	March
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How to Become an Effective Science-policy Advisor? 16 Lessons Learned	March
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Interdisciplinarity for the Net-Zero Transition	April
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OPEN SCIENCE

Science Europe Conference Report on Open Science	May
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Joint statement: Council conclusions on not-for-profit scholarly communication ecosystem	May
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Diamond Open Access – Conclusions and Way Forward	November
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CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

Statement on International Research Collaboration	December
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Briefing on Identifying Relevant Aspects to Monitor the Benefits and Impacts of Cross-border Collaboration (Members Only)	December
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TITLE	PUBLICATION DATE
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EU LEGISLATION

Call for Caution in Discussing Phasing Out of the Use of Animals in Research	July
--	------

RESEARCH ASSESSMENT

Recognising What We Value : Recommendations on Recognition Systems	April
--	-------

SCIENCE COMMUNICATION

Communications Roadmap (Members Only)	May
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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Report of Internal Workshop on Artificial Intelligence in Science (Members Only)	December
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OTHER

2022 Annual Report: Research at the Heart of Europe's Ambition	June
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SCIENCE EUROPE'S MAIN EVENTS 2023

TITLE	DATE
Internal Workshop on Science Communication	26–27 January
Science–Policy in Action for the Green and Digital Transition	29 March
1st Webinar for the Diamond Open Access community	17 April
Webinar on Science for Net-Zero	20 April
Webinar on Open Research Methods	6 September
2nd Webinar for the Diamond Open Access community	18 September
Session at the Science Summit during the 78th UN General Assembly	20 September
Internal Webinar on Artificial Intelligence	28 September
Global Summit on Diamond Open Access	23–27 October
2nd Conference on Diamond Open Access	25–26 October
2023 GRC European Regional Meeting	20–21 November
High Level Workshop on ERA 2023	29–30 November
Inception Workshop for the DIAMAS Project	4 December

Colophon

2023 SCIENCE EUROPE ANNUAL REPORT:

FROM AMBITION TO ACTION: FOSTERING RESEARCH EXCELLENCE IN EUROPE

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Lead Author: Rosemary Hindle, Science Europe

Co-Authors: Adrien Braem, Sara Cesari, Nicola Francesco Dotti, Sophie Lemahieu, James Morris, Bregt Saenen

Editors: Lidia Borrell-Damián, Rosemary Hindle, Iwan Groeneveld

Designer: edito3

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RUE DE LA SCIENCE 14, 1040 BRUSSELS, BELGIUM

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